

Additional file 7.

Probability of complete assembly of *msp1* block 2 is dependent on depth of coverage. Dummy reads were generated *in silico* from the Palo Alto allelic sequence of *msp1* block 2 at 10 different coverage depths. Reads were generated 10 times for each coverage depth and then assembled using Velvet, and the presence of the complete block 2 sequence was determined. The probability of assembling the whole *msp1* block 2 sequence is shown. There is a strong and significant correlation between coverage depth and the probability of complete assembly of the Palo Alto *msp1* block 2 sequence ($\rho = 0.96$, $p < 0.001$).